

STRONG AND TOUGH FUNGAL BASED CHITIN-GLUCAN THIN FILM

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ABSTRACT

Fungal cell walls are rich in structural fibers made of chitin and glucan. These fibers were covalently linked, forming a ready-made nanocomposite fabric which is potentially useful in the development of a single-sourced bioreinforcement material that combines the strength of chitin and the toughness of glucan. In this study, chitin-glucan material was extracted from common mushroom fruiting body (*Agaricus bisporus*) and tree bracket fungus (*Daedaleopsis confragosa*) followed by thin film sheet production. Their morphological, chemical, and mechanical properties were compared. Extracts from common mushroom were found to be readily disintegrated into nanofiber dimension (10-20 nm wide, several μm long) without any post-mechanical treatment, while the microfiber dimension is more prevalent in tree bracket fungus extract (1-2 μm wide, several μm long). Homogenous dispersion was achieved with the aid of a domestic blender prior to vacuum filtration during thin film preparation. It was found that the ratio of chitin to glucan in common mushroom nearly equal at 40:50, while glucan predominates in tree bracket fungus (chitin to glucan ratio, 1:99). This translate to distinct mechanical properties, in which strong film having tensile strength of ~ 200 MPa were produced from common mushroom extract, while tough film with elongation at break exceeding 10% was produced from tree fungus extract. Subsequently, the effect of combining these two fungal extract at different proportion towards mechanical properties of thin film were also investigated.

1 INTRODUCTION

Chitin is a fibrous biopolymer that made up crustacean shell, insect exoskeleton, and fungal cell wall. It is renewable, biodegradable, and non-toxic material with abundance second only to cellulose. To date, chitin and its main derivatives, chitosan have been used extensively as heavy metal and dye chelating agent in wastewater treatment, as sutures and wound-dressing in medical field, and as additive and stabilizer in food industry [1]

Due to its fibrous nature, chitin can be defibrillated into nanofiber or further hydrolyzed into whiskers, introducing more sites for hydrogen bonding which can lead to production of stronger yet greener material. This concept is very much in line with growing public's demand for more environmentally friendly material and many governmental visions to reduce dependency on petroleum based materials. Nair and Dufresne [2] has shown that incorporation of 20% chitin whisker into unvulcanized natural rubber improve the rubbery modulus by 350 times while addition of 5% chitin improve thermal stability of the composite significantly up to 230°C. Ifuku et al [3] reported an increase of 3 GPa moduli and 20 MPa in strength for acrylic resin filled with 40% chitin nanofiber. On its own, chitin film has been shown to possess modulus and strength between 3-8 GPa and 50-150 MPa, respectively [4-6]. More research has been carried out in order to realize the potential of single fiber chitin chain modulus that peaked at 60 GPa [7].

In contrast with animal chitin, chitin derived from fungal biomass is covalently linked with another structural biopolymer, β -glucan [8]. The extent of chitin to glucan proportion varies between fungal species and also very much governed by external factor such cultivation environment, pH, cell wall stress, etc. [9]. These consequently affect the mechanical performance of resulting fiber if it is going to be used for green material fabrication. Although the existence of glucan may complicate further analysis, its presence also means it is now possible to develop a composite without any additional matrix. Furthermore, chitin derived from fungal sources can offer several advantages over crustacean chitin such as: (1) free from allergenic shellfish protein, (2) faster growth-cycle rate, (3) no need for demineralized step during extraction process, thus reducing overall operational cost, and (4) not subjected to crustacean seasonal fluctuation and sea pollution.

In present work, chitin-glucan complex were extracted from 2 fungal sources, namely common mushroom, *A. bisporus*, and polypore bracket fungus, *D. confragosa*. This is followed by subsequent thin film fabrication and characterization in term of morphology, chemical constituent, and mechanical performance. Finally, a composite bearing mixture of both fungal extract at different proportion were prepared and studied.

2 MATERIALS & METHODS

2.1 Fungi samples and chitin-glucan extraction

Common white mushroom, *A. bisporus*, having average cap diameter of 5-7cm were purchased from local store. It was weighed and kept frozen before further use to prevent water losses and enzymatic degradation. Prior to extraction, frozen samples were first soaked in excess water for 5 min and rinsed to remove any observable impurities. The procedure was repeated three times followed by initial blending in high-speed blender (Breville VBL065 Pro 800W, Oldham, UK) for 5 min. Resulted slurry were heated at 85°C for 30 min (w:v , 1:30) followed by centrifugation at 7000 rpm for 15 min (ThermoScientific, Sorvall Legend RT+). Residual cake was treated with 1 M NaOH (w:v , 1:30) for 3 hour at 65°C. The slurry was then successively re-centrifuged in excess water until neutral pH was obtained. Finally, the neutralized alkali insoluble cake were resuspended in water at 0.8% w/v and dispersed by final blending for another 1 min.

Tree bracket fungi, *D. confragosa*, a polypore fungus commonly found on decayed willow tree were obtained from open shrub during autumn season. The bracket is characteristically tough with leathery texture, brownish in color and having width approximately 10-12 cm. It was soaked in distilled water overnight before being diced to average dimension of 1 mm x 10 mm. The extraction procedure is similar to common mushroom mentioned above, except 10 min and 30 min are used for initial and final blending, respectively.

2.2 Preparation of thin film

Chitin-glucan suspension were weighed corresponding to final thin film specification (80 gsm grammage, 90 mm diameter) followed by vacuum filtration through cellulose filter paper (VWR 413, 5-13 μ m retention value). Resulted filter cake was then wet pressed between blotting paper (3MM

CHR blotting paper, VWR) to remove excess water before pressed one final time before hot pressed under 5 kg weight in the oven for 3 hours at 120°C.

2.3 Chemical analysis

Carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, sulphur and oxygen content by mass were determined by elemental analyzer (EA 1108 CHNS-O, Carlo Erba Instruments). Carbohydrate analysis was carried out by High Performance Anion Exchange chromatography (HPEAC). Briefly, 300 mg of freeze dried sample was mixed with 3 ml of 72% sulphuric acid at 30°C for 60 minutes. The acid was then diluted with water to 4% concentration and the mixture was placed in an autoclave at 121°C for 60 minutes. The HPEAC was performed to the hydrolysate with a Dionex ICS3000 chromatograph equipped with a CarboPac PA20 column (Dionex, Sunnyvale, CA, USA). Sugar Recovery Standards (SRS) were prepared and pre-treated in identical hydrolysis conditions prior to HPAEC analysis in order to analyze their recovery throughout the procedure.

2.4 Morphological analysis

Morphology of extracted nanofibers was studied using a high-resolution field emission gun scanning electron microscope (LEO Gemini 1525 FEG-SEM, Oberkochen, Germany). The accelerating voltage used was 5 kV. Prior to SEM, 3µl of chitin samples in water suspension was dropped onto 400 mesh TEM copper grid on carbon tabs stuck on the SEM stubs, air dried and Cr coated (K550 sputter coater, Emitech Ltd., Ashford, Kent, UK) for 30 sec at 80 mA. Thin film sample also investigated.

2.5 Mechanical analysis

Thin films were cut into dog bone shape specimens using Zwick cutter. The test specimen possesses an overall length of 35 mm and the narrowest part of the specimen is 2 mm, with 10 mm gauge length. Prior to the test, the specimens were secured onto testing cards using a two-part cold curing epoxy resin (Araldite 2011, Huntsman Advanced Materials, Cambridge, U.K.). This was to prevent the clamp of the tensile testing equipment from damaging the test specimens while spreading the stress concentrations in order to avoid premature failure initiation sites.

Tensile test was conducted using a TST350 tensile tester (Linkam Scientific Instruments, Surrey, UK). The load cell and crosshead speed used were 200 N and 1 mm.min⁻¹, respectively. The sample thickness was determined using handheld microscope on polished epoxy embedded sample, calibrated using 100 x 0.01=1 mm microscope graticule (Graticules Ltd., Tonbridge, Kent, UK). A total of 5 specimens were tested for each type of nanopaper. The machine compliance was determined to be 6.38 x 10⁻³ mm.N⁻¹.

3 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1 Chemical analysis

Mild extraction was adopted in this study in order to preserve the native quality of chitin-based fiber. Prolonged acid treatments during demineralisation step are known to degrade chitin chain while longer duration of deproteination resulted towards higher degree of chitin deacetylation [10, 11]. While acid treatment is essential for CaCO₃ removal during chitin extraction from crustacean source, this step is often eliminated for fungal sources due to lack of mineralization [12-14]. This can significantly reduce an overall processing cost and consumption of hazardous chemical.

Table 1 shows the yield and corresponding elemental analysis of each fungal source extracts. Chitin-glucan made up 1.0-1.5% of fresh common mushroom. This low yield is attributed by the fact that 90% of fresh mushroom is water. This value is much lower than the amount of chitin that can be extracted from crustacean origin, which typically give 8-33% yield [15]. For example, in this study, about 70 g fresh mushrooms is required to produce one 80 gsm, 120 mm diameter thin film, while only ~10 g crab shell is needed to produce similar sample. This lower yield is compensated by

mushroom's faster growth rate, averaging 2-3 weeks to reach maturity compared to 6-12 month needed for crustacean like crab. Chitin-glucan yield from tree bracket fungi is higher than common mushroom as less water is required to support its fruiting body growth.

Source	C (%)	O (%)	H (%)	N (%)	S (%)	Yield ¹ (%)
<i>A. bisporus</i> stalk	42.22	44.45	7.24	2.95	0.02	15.39
<i>A. bisporus</i> cap	42.87	43.36	7.20	3.28	0.02	11.19
Bracket fungi	43.25	50.55	6.51	0.24	0.02	58.17

¹The yield is based on dry weight basis

Table 1: Chitin/chitin-glucan yield of each sample and its corresponding elemental analysis.

One main difference between fungal chitin and crustacean chitin is the existence of β 1-3 and β 1-6 linked glucan. Glucose (precursor for β -glucan) is typically absent in crustacean chitin, but made up almost half of extract from mushroom source and more than 95 % of bracket fungi (Table 2). Glucosamine (precursor for chitin and chitosan) were found to be almost absent in bracket fungi. This characteristic is very similar to yeast, another fungal source that typically comprise of 99% glucan and 1% chitin inside their cell wall. It was found that the ratio between chitin and glucan play a significant role towards characteristic of prepared thin film. Film that consist higher fungal chitin ratio was found to be more brittle, while the opposite was the case for the film that consist of higher amount of glucan.

Source	Galactose (%)	Glucose (%)	Xylose (%)	Mannose (%)	Glucosamine (%)	Total sugars (%)
<i>A. bisporus</i> stalk	0.2	46.8	1.0	5.8	29.8	83.6
<i>A. bisporus</i> cap	0.4	39.6	0.9	6.5	32.3	79.7
Bracket fungi	0.0	96.8	0.0	0.0	1.1	97.9

¹Arabinose and Rhamnose is not detected.

²Total sugar is less than 100% due to other non-carbohydrate moieties, i.e. protein

Table 2: Monosaccharide composition of extracted chitin-glucan from each sample.

3.2 Morphological analysis

SEM images of thin film surface are shown in Figure 1. Extract from common mushrooms readily assume nanofiber dimension (20-30 nm wide, several μ m long) after chemical extraction. No post-mechanical defibrillation was attempted except 1 min blending was used to assist homogenous redispersion in water. Ifuku [16] obtain 20-28 nm width chitin nanofiber from different mushroom, using grinding under acidic condition as defibrillation method. We have shown here, simple blending using domestic blender under mild extraction procedure was enough to nanofibrillate the chitin from common white mushroom. In contrast, fiber extracts from bracket fungi were in microfibril region (1-2 μ m wide, several μ m long). Additional blending for 30 minute using domestic blender was unable to defibrillate these fibers, which suggest strong adhesion between glucan fibril. Higher shearing force by means of homogenization or colloidizer can be used to further nanofibrillate the fibers in order to expose more area for stronger hydrogen bonding during thin film production.

Figure 2 shows SEM images of thin film composite of whole mushroom chitin-glucan extract and bracket fungi extract. Coat of mushroom nanofiber can be seen enveloping the bracket fungi microfibril and thicker coat is evidence when the ratio of mushroom nanofiber is increased.

Figure 1: (a) *A. bisporus* chitin-glucan extract thin film (b) *D. confragosa* chitin-glucan extract thin film.

Figure 2: (a) 25% ABW 75% BF (b) 50% ABW 50% BF (c) 75% ABW 25% BF (d) fracture image of 50% ABW 50% BF ; ABW= *A. bisporus* whole, BF = bracket fungi

No aggregations of microfiber were observed even at higher ratio of mushroom nanofiber. This might be attributed by distinct dimension difference between the two. During initial suspension filtration, heavy microfiber will settle at the bottom first, creating a porous micronetwork. This is followed by pore-filling by mushroom nanofiber which reduces the filtration rate significantly while simultaneously cement the position of bracket fungi micronetwork. The nanofiber coat will then formed slowly on top of 'cemented' microfiber without displacing it too much, assuring homogenous dispersion. Fracture image (Figure 2 (d)) of thin film composite shows the nanofiber interlaced with microfiber in layered fashion.

3.3 Mechanical analysis

Figure 3 shows the stress-strain curve behavior of representative thin film/thin film composite under uniaxial force. Non-linear behavior was observed for every sample, which suggests the occurrence of fiber slippage that may be attributed by difference conformation between glucan and chitin polymer inside the fibril. The tensile properties are summarized in Table 3.

Neat film derived from mushroom chitin-glucan is generally stronger, while films derived from bracket fungi were found to be tougher. This might be attributed by chitin-glucan ratio of the sample, in which higher chitin ratio results in higher strength and stiffness. For mushroom film, extract from stalk produce tougher thin film than the cap, although there is not much difference in overall tensile strength. Higher thin film elongation in stalk is expected as during growth of mushroom, cell elongation predominantly occurs in stipe region which might promotes longer chitin fiber synthesis, whereas cell expansion is more predominant in cap region [17, 18]. These longer fibers were able to absorb more energy before failure in comparison to shorter fiber from cap region, as dictated by higher tensile toughness value. This separate information upon properties of stalk and cap is beneficial when one consider the amount of mushroom waste generated industrially, which consist mainly of stalks and mushroom of irregular dimension [14]. Thin film from whole mushrooms extract gave equivalent value in term of tensile strength as stalk and cap, but with reduced elongation percentage. Intertwined long and shorter fiber from both stalk and cap reduce overall fiber rotational mobility might be the reason for stiffer thin film.

The effect of changing chitin-glucan ratio on mechanical performance of thin film was observed by making a composite. Increasing chitin content by means of increasing the ratio of whole mushrooms extract on bracket fungi extract, increase the modulus of the sample at the expense of reduced elongation and toughness. For instance, an addition of 25% mushroom chitin increase thin film modulus by twofold, but reduce the elongation and toughness by half. Subsequent addition of mushroom chitin gradually increases the toughness as a result of subsequent increase in tensile strength.

Figure 3: Stress-strain curve of representative neat thin film and thin film composite

	Tensile strength (Mpa)	Young modulus (Gpa)	Elongation (%)	Tensile toughness (MJ.m ⁻³)
Thin film				
<i>A. bisporus</i> stalk	191.88 ± 10.60	5.02 ± 0.31	9.24 ± 1.34	10.04 ± 1.57
<i>A. bisporus</i> cap	192.87 ± 12.01	5.21 ± 0.46	7.44 ± 1.52	7.88 ± 1.73
<i>A. bisporus</i> whole (ABW)	204.38 ± 4.01	7.33 ± 0.82	5.28 ± 0.39	5.30 ± 0.51
Bracket fungi (BF)	61.92 ± 2.84	1.15 ± 0.14	13.92 ± 0.68	5.83 ± 0.56
Thin film composite				
ABW25BF75	82.74 ± 4.24	2.57 ± 0.25	6.34 ± 0.48	2.98 ± 0.37
ABW50BF50	114.76 ± 4.23	3.92 ± 0.22	5.70 ± 0.28	3.52 ± 0.31
ABW75BF25	136.00 ± 5.97	4.69 ± 0.52	6.10 ± 0.17	4.48 ± 0.25

Table 3: Mechanical properties of neat thin film and thin film composite

4 CONCLUSIONS

Thin films were prepared from common mushroom and tree bracket fungi extract. Distinct difference in fiber morphology, chemical constituent and mechanical properties were observed between the two. Nanofiber with equal amount of chitin and glucan were extracted from common mushroom. In contrast, microfibril was more prevalent in bracket fungi extract, which mainly comprise of glucan. Thin film composite was prepared to investigate the effect of chitin-glucan ratio towards mechanical performance. Addition of chitin was found to increase the stiffness of thin film, while addition of glucan toughens the specimen.

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